

Novel results from the sodium borohydride reduction of *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides in methanol : formation of an interesting class of chromanone-derived methoxydiols[†]

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Abstract : Sodium borohydride reduction of a number of *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides in methanol gave an interesting class of methoxydiols characterized as 3(*S**),4(*S**)-dihydroxy-3-[α (*R**)-methoxybenzyl]chromans, along with the corresponding *cis*-epoxyalcohols. Mechanistic pathway for the formation of the new type of methoxydiols has been suggested to be methoxide-induced opening of the epoxide ring of an intermediate related to the *trans*-epoxyalcohols. Sodium borohydride reduction of *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone epoxide also gave similar results.

Keywords : *E*-3-Benzylidenechromanone epoxides, sodium borohydride reduction, *cis*-*E*-3-benzylidene-4-hydroxychroman epoxides, 3(*S**),4(*S**)-dihydroxy-3-[α (*R**)-methoxybenzyl]chromans, mechanism.

Introduction

Both natural and synthetic chroman derivatives show diverse biological activities¹⁻⁷, some being in regular clinical use^{8,9}. This has made the chemistry of chromanones and related compounds an area of research interest to organic chemists with the goal of generating new biologically active molecules. Recently, we have reported two eco-friendly synthesis of *E*-3-benzylidenechromanones (**1**)^{10a,b} and their facile conversion to 3-(α -hydroxybenzyl)chromones and 3-benzoylchromones using NBS as the oxidant^{10c}. Depending upon the amount of NBS used (1 equiv. or 2 equiv.), 3-(α -hydroxybenzyl)chromones or 3-benzoylchromones were found to be the major product of the reaction. Like other α,β -unsaturated ketones, *E*-3-

benzylidenechromanones (**1**) can be readily converted to their epoxides¹¹. Considering the versatility of the synthetic applications of epoxyalcohols^{11a,12}, we undertook a research program involving the synthesis of a number of *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides (**2**) and study of their sodium borohydride reduction in methanol with a view to getting epoxyalcohols of the chroman series. This simple research problem, expected to produce two stereoisomeric epoxyalcohols in unequal amounts, gave some unexpected results. Sodium borohydride reduction of **4**, the epoxide of *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone (**3**), done analogously, followed a similar path. The outcome of these studies is presented herein.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Results and discussion

When *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxide (**2a**) was reduced with sodium borohydride in dry methanol, two products were formed – the first one was an epoxyalcohol, while the other, instead of being a stereoisomer of the former, possessed some conspicuous structural features. This product was found to contain a methoxy group, for the origin of which, the involvement of solvent methanol was logically made responsible. That this unusual product did not originate via the isolated epoxyalcohol was confirmed from the occurrence of no reaction by heating the latter with sodium methoxide or sodium borohydride

in methanol. The study was then extended to five more *E*-benzylidenechromanone epoxides (**2b-f**) and in all these cases analogous results were obtained (Table 1).

A thorough literature survey done in this connection revealed that there is only one previous report¹³ of formation of 2-methoxy-1,3-diol system (**6**) during sodium borohydride reduction of vicinal epoxyketones (**5**) (Scheme 1). In two other instances, 2,3-epoxyalcohol systems having *trans* orientation of the epoxy and OH groups were found to be converted to 2-methoxy-1,3-diols^{14,15} on treatment with sodium borohydride in methanol (Scheme 2).

For sodium borohydride reduction of *E*-3-benzylidene-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

chromanone epoxides (**2**), the orientation of the epoxide ring appears to be the only controlling factor for approach of BH_4^- to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$. So, it was considered that each of **2a-f** would undergo hydride attack at the corresponding $\text{C}=\text{O}$ from both sides, side of the epoxy ring or opposite, resulting in two diastereomeric epoxyalcohols in unequal amounts.

Analogous to the steroidal epoxyalcohols shown in Scheme 1, the *trans*-epoxyalcohols to be formed here would be expected to be more susceptible to alkoxide-induced epoxide ring opening (through an intermediate alkoxyborohydride complex) than the *cis* isomer. Such a process would generate an unusual product containing a methoxy group in the molecule. However, the way in which the epoxy ring will undergo opening is very important in determining the structure of the product. In the previous examples (Schemes 1 and 2), both the carbons of the epoxy unit were secondary in nature, while in our case the carbon adjacent to the newly generated alcoholic grouping is tertiary and the other is secondary. Since an $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ attack on a tertiary carbon is very much disfavored, we envisaged that here the epoxide ring opening would take place in the other possible way resulting in a tertiary alcohol of the type **8**. That this was the actual situation was evident from the results of acetylation of the new methoxy compounds. Thus, two of such compounds (**8b** and **8f**) were subjected to acetylation reactions when it

was found that each of them formed a monoacetate (instead of a diacetate formation shown by some steroidal methoxydiols^{13,14}). The suggested mechanistic pathway for formation of **7** and **8** is delineated in Scheme 3.

We then studied the borohydride reduction of *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone epoxide (**4**) (a carbocyclic analog of **2a**) in methanol. It was very interesting to note that in this case also, two products, an epoxyalcohol **9** and a methoxydiol **10** (analogous to **7** and **8**, respectively) resulted (Table 1).

In continuation of the above study, sodium borohydride reduction of **2a**, **2b** and **2d** were performed in primary alcohols other than methanol (Table 2). In each of these cases, the *cis*-epoxyalcohol (**7**) was obtained in a yield comparable to that in the reduction in methanol. Reduction of **2b** in allyl alcohol and *n*-butanol afforded the corresponding *trans*-epoxyalcohol (**11b**) as the second product in low yield. However, for reduction in ethanol, any pure second product could not be obtained even after several careful chromatographies over silica gel or neutral alumina. An examination of the ^1H NMR spectra of the impure products thus obtained revealed that the major component of each of them was a 3(*S**),4(*S**)-dihydroxy-3-[α (*R**)-ethoxybenzyl]-6-methylchroman (**12**). Possibly, **12** containing a larger alkoxy group at the α -position is somewhat less stable¹⁴ than **8** and undergoes

Scheme 3

Table 1. Products of NaBH₄ reduction of *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides (2) and *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone epoxide (4) in methanol

Entry	Substrate	Product 1 [Yield (%)]	Product 2 [Yield (%)]
1	2a	 7a [41]	 8a [36]
2	2b	 7b [37]	 8b [30]
3	2c	 7c [43]	 8c [26]
4	2d	 7d [40]	 8d [32]
5	2e	 7e [45]	 8e [40]
6	2f	 7f [41]	 8f [35]
7	4	 9 [42]	 10 [39]

change to **11** and/or some related compound during column chromatography, making the purification process difficult.

Table 2. Products of NaBH₄ reduction of *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides (2) in alcohols other than methanol

Entry	Substrate	Alcohol used	Product 1 [Yield (%)]	Product 2 [Yield (%)]
1	2b		7b [38]	11b [19]
2	2b	<i>n</i> -BuOH	7b [41]	11b [21]
3	2a	EtOH	7a [37]	12a ^a
4	2b	EtOH	7b [40]	12b ^a
5	2d	EtOH	7d [35]	12d ^a

^aMajor component of a product mixture (from ¹H NMR).

The assigned structures of the unusual alkoxydiols obtained from *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides (2a-f) and *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone epoxide (4) are based mainly on their spectral data and the result of acetylation reaction on two of them. However, there is scope of the initially formed reduction product **11** having *trans* orientation of the epoxy and hydroxyl groups to undergo change to an isomeric epoxyalcohol **13** by Payne rearrangement¹⁶ in the reaction medium which is slightly alkaline. If that be the case and epoxide ring opening of **13** becomes significantly faster than that of **11**, the said unusual compounds would have the structure **14** (Scheme 4). X-Ray crystallographic study of at least one of the alkoxydiols isolated by us could have settled the structural and mechanistic aspects unambiguously. However, in spite of our best effort, so far we could not get good quality crystals for any one of the borohydride reduction products of the epoxyketones **2** and **4**.

Conclusion

Some very interesting aspects of sodium borohydride reduction of *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides (2) and *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone epoxide (4) are evident from the work presented herein. Unlike the previously known

a : R¹ = R² = H; b : R¹ = Me, R² = H; c : R¹ = Me, R² = Cl;
d : R¹ = Cl, R² = H; e : R¹ = Cl, R² = Cl; f : R¹ = Cl, R² = Br

Scheme 4

examples (Schemes 1 and 2), here a *trans*-2,3-epoxyalcohol system is undergoing methoxide-induced epoxide opening through a six membered cyclic transition state leading to a 3-methoxy-1,2-diol system. All the epoxyalcohols (7 and 9) and methoxydiols (8 and 10) encountered in this study are new compounds and they might have interesting biological activities.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on a Köfler block and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer (Spectrum BX II) in KBr pellets. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Bruker AV-300 (300 MHz) spectrometer.

Analytical samples were routinely dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Microanalytical data were recorded on two Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series II C, H, N analyzers. Mass spectra were measured in the following ways : ESIMS(+) [Waters Micromass Q-ToF microTM], FAB-MS [Jeol the M Station JMS.700]. Column chromatography was performed with silica gel (100–200 mesh) and TLC with silica gel G made of SRL Pvt. Ltd. Petroleum ether had the boiling range 60–80 °C.

Preparation of E-3-benzylidenechromanones (1) and *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone (3) :

E-3-Benzylidenechromanones (1)/*E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone (3) required in this study were prepared by condensation of chromanones/1-tetralone with benzaldehydes by either HCl-catalysed^{10c} or amberlyst-15-catalyzed^{10a} methods.

Preparation of E-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxides (2) and *E*-2-benzylidene-1-tetralone epoxide (4) :

Aqueous NaOH (10%, 15 ml) and H₂O₂ (30%, 7 ml) were added to a suspension of an *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone (2 g) in ethanol (95%, 50 ml), the mixture was stirred for 4 h and then allowed to stand for 12 h. The crude product separated was collected, washed with

water, dried and subjected to column chromatography over neutral alumina to get the corresponding *E*-3-benzylidenechromanone epoxide (2) in pure state. *E*-2-Benzylidene-1-tetralone epoxide (4) was prepared by the same procedure. All these epoxides were characterized from their ¹H NMR spectral data as given below :

E-3-Benzylidenechromanone epoxide (2a) : Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 133–134 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.12 (1H, d, *J* 12.4 Hz, H-2a), 4.56 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.58 (1H, s, H-α), 6.94 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-8), 7.09 (1H, br t, *J* 7.8 Hz, H-6), 7.34–7.42 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.52 (1H, dt, *J* 8.7 and 1.8 Hz, H-7), 7.98 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8 and 1.5 Hz, H-5).

E-3-Benzylidene-6-methylchromanone epoxide (2b) : Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 128–130 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.34 (3H, s, Me), 4.09 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-2a), 4.54 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.56 (1H, s, H-α), 6.86 (1H, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-8), 7.24–7.43 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.77 (1H, br s, H-5).

E-3-(4-Chlorobenzylidene)-6-methylchromanone epoxide (2c) : Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 132–133 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.33 (3H, s, Me), 4.04 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2a), 4.51 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.53 (1H, s, H-α), 6.86 (1H, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.26–7.41 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.76 (1H, br s, H-5).

E-3-Benzylidene-6-chlorochromanone epoxide (2d) : Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 170–172 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.13 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2a), 4.54 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz, H-2b), 4.58 (1H, s, H-α), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.33–7.48 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.93 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-5).

E-6-Chloro-3-(4-chlorobenzylidene)chromanone epoxide (2e) : Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 151–153 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.08 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz, H-2a), 4.54 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.54 (1H, s, H-α), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-8), 7.28 (2H, br d, *J* 8.1 Hz,

H-2', 6'), 7.41 (2H, br d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-3', 5'), 7.47 (1H, dd, *J* 8.8 and 2.6 Hz, H-7), 7.93 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-5).

E-3-(4-Bromobenzylidene)-6-chlorochromanone epoxide (2f) : Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 154–155 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.08 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz, H-2a), 4.52 (1H, s, H-α), 4.53 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* 8.9 Hz, H-8), 7.23 (2H, br d, *J* 8.3 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.47 (1H, dd, *J* 8.8 and 2.6 Hz, H-7), 7.56 (2H, br d, *J* 8.3 Hz, H-3', 5'), 9.93 (1H, d, *J* 2.6 Hz, H-5).

E-2-Benzylidene-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene-1-one epoxide (4) : Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 74–75 °C (Lit.¹⁷ 76–77.5 °C); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.87 (1H, m, H-3a), 2.45 (1H, m, H-3b), 2.83 (2H, m, H-4a and H-4b), 4.36 (1H, s, H-α), 7.20–7.54 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, br d, *J* 7.8 Hz, H-5).

General procedure for sodium borohydride reduction of 2 and 4 :

To a solution of an appropriate epoxide (200 mg) of the said categories in a dry alcohol (30 ml), NaBH₄ (80 mg) was added gradually. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 20 h. It was then poured into ice water, acidified with dilute HCl and extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 ml). The concentrate of the dichloromethane extract was subjected to rapid column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate mixtures of increasing polarity as eluents to get the products in pure form. Finally the solid products were crystallized from dichloromethane-petroleum ether.

cis-E-3-Benzylidene-4-hydroxychroman epoxide (7a) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 125–127 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3257 (O-H), 2921, 2361, 1584, 1483, 1459, 1366, 1270, 1220, 1121, 1041, 1017, 916, 862, 743 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.20 (1H, br s, O-H), 4.00 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-2a), 4.06 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.47 (1H, s, H-α), 4.94 (1H, s, H-4), 6.85 (1H, br d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-8), 7.00 (1H, dt, *J* 8.1 and 1.5 Hz, H-6), 7.23 (1H, dt, *J* 7.2 and 1.5 Hz, H-7), 7.37 (5H, br s, C₆H₅), 7.50 (1H, br d, *J* 7.2 Hz, H-5) (Found : C, 75.12; H, 5.75. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄O₃ : C, 75.57; H, 5.55%).

cis-E-3-Benzylidene-4-hydroxy-6-methylchroman epoxide (7b) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 114–116 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3250 (O-H), 2925, 2355, 1574, 1499, 1463, 1352,

1245, 1215, 1124, 1040, 1027, 906, 855, 745 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.71 (1H, br s, O-H), 2.31 (3H, s, Me), 3.96 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2a), 4.05 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.47 (1H, s, H-α), 4.91 (1H, s, H-4), 6.74 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-8), 7.03 (1H, br d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.25–7.39 (6H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 30.8, 60.1, 61.7, 64.7, 64.8, 118.2, 125.7, 126.1, 126.3, 128.3, 128.47, 128.52, 129.6, 133.3, 152.6 (Found : C, 75.80; H, 6.25. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆O₃ : C, 76.10; H, 6.01%).

cis-E-3-(4-Chlorobenzylidene)-4-hydroxy-6-methylchroman epoxide (7c) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 137–138 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.31 (3H, s, Me), 3.92 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-2a), 4.02 (1H, d, *J* 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.42 (1H, s, H-α), 4.91 (1H, s, H-4), 6.76 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, H-8), 7.03 (1H, br d, *J* 8.2 Hz, H-7), 7.26–7.38 (5H, m, Ar-H).

cis-E-3-Benzylidene-6-chloro-4-hydroxychroman epoxide (7d) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 148–150 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3227 (O-H), 2924, 2361, 1577, 1486, 1483, 1363, 1264, 1220, 1164, 1092, 1007, 943, 855, 747 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.29 (1H, br peak, O-H), 4.02 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz, H-2a), 4.05 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz, H-2b), 4.49 (1H, s, H-α), 4.96 (1H, s, H-4), 6.74 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.15 (1H, dd, *J* 8.7 and 2.6 Hz, H-7), 7.34–7.42 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.50 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, H-5); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 59.6, 61.1, 64.1, 64.3, 117.6, 125.1, 125.6, 125.8, 127.8, 127.9, 128.0, 129.1, 132.8, 152.1; MS (TOF MS ES⁺) : Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃ClO₃ (M+Na)⁺ : 311.72; found 311.73 (Found : C, 66.80; H, 4.65. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃ClO₃ : C, 66.56; H, 4.54%).

cis-E-3-(4-Chlorobenzylidene)-6-chloro-4-hydroxychroman epoxide (7e) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 173–175 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3253 (O-H), 2890, 2360, 1579, 1483, 1480, 1356, 1260, 1223, 1179, 1095, 1092, 938, 869, 760 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.26 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz, O-H), 3.96 (1H, d, *J* 12.4 Hz, H-2a), 4.02 (1H, d, *J* 12.4 Hz, H-2b), 4.45 (1H, s, H-α), 4.93 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz, H-4), 6.80 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.18 (1H, dd, *J* 8.7 and 2.7 Hz, H-7), 7.30 (2H, br d, *J* 8.2 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.37

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(1H, br d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-3', 5'), 7.49 (1H, br d, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-5); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 59.7, 61.9, 64.5, 64.7, 118.2, 125.5, 126.4, 127.5, 128.5, 128.8, 129.8, 131.5, 131.9, 134.4, 152.6.

cis-E-3-(4-Bromobenzylidene)-6-chloro-4-hydroxychroman epoxide (7f) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 184–185 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3277 (O-H), 3155, 2331, 1475, 1275, 1216, 1011, 943, 814 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.29 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz, OH), 3.96 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz H-2a), 4.01 (1H, d, *J* 12.6 Hz, H-2b), 4.43 (1H, s, H-α), 4.93 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-4), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.18 (1H, dd, *J* 8.7 and 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.25 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-3', 5'), 7.53 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-8) (Found : C, 51.98; H, 3.48. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂BrClO₃ : C, 52.27; H, 3.29%).

Acetylation (Ac₂O/Py, room temp., 48 h) of **7f** gave a monoacetate, colorless semisolid, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.17 (3H, s, OCOMe), 3.63 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-2a), 4.24 (1H, s, H-α), 4.39 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-2b), 5.78 (1H, s, H-4), 6.78 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.16 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.21 (1H, dd, *J* 8.7 and 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.33 (1H, d, *J* 2.8, H-5), 7.51 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-3', 5').

cis-E-2-Benzylidene-1-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene epoxide (9) :

Colorless semisolid, IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3226 (O-H), 2922, 2897, 2882, 1647, 1496, 1486, 1400, 1356, 1260, 1179, 1092, 1013, 938, 845, 762 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.76–1.96 (2H, m, >CH₂), 2.63–2.86 (2H, m, >CH₂), 4.47 (1H, s, H-α), 4.89 (1H, s, H-1), 7.08–7.43 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.60 (1H, br d, *J* 7.3 Hz, H-8).

3(S), 4(S*)-Dihydroxy-3-[α(R*)-methoxybenzyl]chroman (8a)* :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 122–123 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3443 (OH), 2926, 2824, 1613, 1588, 1490, 1466, 1455, 1340, 1255, 1233, 1198, 1084, 1031, 952, 875, 851, 739 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.99 (2H, br peak, OH at C-3 and C-4), 3.26 (3H, s, OMe), 3.89 (1H, s, H-α/H-4), 4.34 (1H, d, *J* 11.7 Hz, H-2a), 4.45 (1H, d, *J* 11.7 Hz, H-2b), 4.46 (1H, s, H-4/H-α), 6.86 (1H, br t, *J* 7.4 Hz, H-6), 6.90 (1H, br d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-8), 7.06 (1H, dd, *J* 7.5 and 1.2 Hz, H-5), 7.21 (1H,

dt, *J* 8.4 and 1.5 Hz, H-7), 7.37–7.44 (3H, m, H-3', 4', 5'), 7.54 (2H, br dd, *J* 7.8 and 1.8 Hz, H-2', 6') (Found : C, 71.12; H, 6.55. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈O₄ : C, 71.31; H, 6.34%).

3(S), 4(S*)-Dihydroxy-3-[α(R*)-methoxybenzyl]-6-methylchroman (8b)* :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 119–120 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3437 (O-H), 3032, 2927, 2892, 2345, 1565, 1482, 1443, 1402, 1333, 1245, 1227, 1089, 1065, 1013, 833, 805, 738 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.20 (3H, s, Me), 3.27 (3H, s, OMe), 3.86 (1H, s, H-α/H-4), 4.32 (1H, d, *J* 11.4 Hz, H-2a), 4.44 (1H, d, *J* 11.4 Hz, H-2b), 4.46 (1H, s, H-4/H-α), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-8), 6.88 (1H, br s, H-5), 7.02 (1H, br d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-7), 7.37–7.43 (3H, m, H-3', 4', 5'), 7.54 (2H, br d, *J* 7.5 Hz, H-2', 6'); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 20.3, 57.0, 66.8, 67.6, 72.6, 83.1, 116.3, 122.0, 128.1, 128.3, 129.0, 130.1, 130.7, 130.8, 135.8, 151.1; MS (TOF MS ES⁺) : Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₀O₄ (M+Na)⁺ : 322.99; found 322.96 (Found : C, 71.67; H, 6.89. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₀O₄ : C, 71.98; H, 6.71%).

Acetylation (Ac₂O/Py, room temp., 48 h) of **8b** gave a monoacetate, colorless semisolid, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.00 (3H, s, OCOMe), 2.21 (3H, s, Me), 2.68 (1H, s, OH), 3.26 (3H, s, OMe), 4.20 (1H, s, H-α), 4.32 (1H, d, *J* 11.9 Hz, H-2a), 4.48 (1H, d, *J* 11.9 Hz, H-2b), 5.14 (1H, s, H-4), 6.78 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-8), 7.03 (1H, dd, *J* 8.7 and 2.5 Hz, H-7), 7.11 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.32–7.54 (5H, m, C₆H₅).

3-[4-Chloro-α(R)-methoxybenzyl]-3(S*), 4(S*)-dihydroxy-6-methylchroman (8c)* :

Colorless semisolid, ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.84 (1H, br s, O-H), 2.20 (3H, s, Me), 2.36 (1H, br s, O-H), 3.25 (3H, s, OMe), 3.79 (1H, br s, H-α/H-4), 4.28 (1H, d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-2a), 4.42 (1H, br d, *J* 12.2 Hz, H-2b), 4.43 (1H, s, H-4/H-α), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-8), 6.86 (1H, br s, H-5), 7.02 (1H, br d, *J* 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.37 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.49 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, H-3', 5').

6-Chloro-3-[α(R)-methoxybenzyl]-3(S*), 4(S*)-dihydroxychroman (8d)* :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 150–152 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.27 (3H, s, OMe), 3.87 (1H, br

s, H- α /H-4), 4.33 (1H, d, J 12.3 Hz, H-2a), 4.43 (1H, br d, J 12.3 Hz, H-2b), 4.44 (1H, s, H-4/H- α), 6.84 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-8), 7.06 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz, H-5), 7.15 (1H, dd, J 8.5 and 1.8 Hz, H-7), 7.36–7.43 (3H, m, H-3', 4', 5'), 7.52 (1H, br dd, J 7.8 and 1.8 Hz, H-2', 6') (Found : C, 63.42; H, 5.54. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₇ClO₄ : C, 63.65; H, 5.34%).

6-Chloro-3-[4-chloro- α (R*)-methoxybenzyl]-3(S*), 4(S*)-dihydroxychroman (8e) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 148–149 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3382 (O-H), 2883, 2360, 1458, 1415, 1244, 1128, 1090, 1064, 1013, 959, 881, 837, 818, 726 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.16 (3H, s, OMe), 3.27 (1H, s, H- α /H-4), 4.41 (2H, s, H-2a and H-2b), 4.87 (1H, s, H-4/H- α), 6.88 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-8), 6.97 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz, H-5), 7.22 (1H, dd, J 8.7 and 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.37 (2H, br d, J 8.6 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.44 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz, H-3', 5') (Found : C, 57.68; H, 4.41. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆Cl₂O₄ : C, 57.48; H, 4.54%).

3-[4-Bromo- α (R*)-methoxybenzyl]-6-chloro-3(S*), 4(S*)-dihydroxychroman (8f) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 142–143 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3537, 3318 (O-H), 2928, 2354, 1413, 1284, 1157, 947, 821 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.91 (1H, br s, OH), 2.40 (1H, br s, OH), 3.25 (3H, s, OMe), 3.80 (1H, s, H- α /H-4), 4.30 (1H, d, J 11.7 Hz, H-2a), 4.39 (1H, s, H-4/H- α), 4.43 (1H, d, J 11.7 Hz, H-2b), 6.84 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.05 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.17 (1H, dd, J 8.7 and 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.40 (2H, br d, J 8.1 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.54 (2H, d, J 8.2 Hz, H-3', 5') (Found : C, 50.85; H, 4.17. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆BrClO₄ : C, 51.09; H, 4.04%).

Acetylation (Ac₂O/Py, room temp., 48 h) of **8f** gave a monoacetate, colorless semisolid, IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3461 (O-H), 2942, 2367, 1745 (ester C=O), 1486, 1221, 1094, 1017, 884, 835 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.01 (3H, s, OCOMe), 2.72 (1H, s, OH), 3.24 (3H, s, OMe), 4.14 (1H, s, H- α), 4.30 (1H, d, J 11.7 Hz, H-2a), 4.47 (1H, d, J 11.7 Hz, H-2b), 5.08 (1H, s, H-4), 6.82 (1H, d, J 8.9 Hz, H-8), 7.18 (1H, dd, J 8.7 and 2.6 Hz, H-7), 7.22 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.29 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.51 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-3', 5').

1(S*), 2(S*)-Dihydroxy-2-[α (R*)-methoxybenzyl]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (10) :

Colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 144–145 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3448 (O-H), 2928, 2827, 1603, 1568, 1494, 1458, 1456, 1342, 1255, 1253, 1188, 1074, 1039, 955, 877, 855, 740 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.34 (2H, m, >CH₂), 2.94 (2H, m, >CH₂), 3.16 (3H, s, OMe), 3.55 (1H, s, H- α /H-1), 4.97 (1H, s, H-1/H- α), 7.01–7.52 (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 75.95; H, 7.49. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₀O₃ : C, 76.03; H, 7.09%).

trans-E-3-Benzylidene-4-hydroxy-6-methylchroman epoxide (11) :

Colorless semisolid, IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3250 (O-H), 2925, 2355, 1574, 1499, 1463, 1352, 1245, 1215, 1124, 1040, 1027, 906, 855, 745 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.31 (3H, s, Me), 3.89 (1H, d, J 12.1 Hz, H-2a), 4.09 (1H, d, J 12.1 Hz, H-2b), 4.48 (1H, s, H- α /H-4), 4.63 (1H, s, H-4/H- α), 6.78 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz, H-8), 7.05 (1H, dd, J 8.2 and 1.9 Hz, H-7), 7.21 (1H, br s, H-5), 7.33–7.39 (5H, m, Ar-H).

3-[α (R*)-Ethoxybenzyl]-3(S*), 4(S*)-dihydroxychroman (12a) :

This compound could not be obtained in pure state. From a careful analysis of the ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) spectral data of the impure material the following assignments have been derived : δ 1.16 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz, -OCH₂-CH₃), 3.06–3.12 (1H, m, H-a of CH₂ of -OCH₂-CH₃), 3.48–3.54 (1H, m, H-b of CH₂ of -OCH₂-CH₃), 3.54 (1H, br s, H- α /H-4), 4.43 (1H, d, J 12.3 Hz, H-2a), 4.50 (1H, d, J 12.1 Hz, H-2b), 4.93 (1H, s, H-4/H- α), 6.83–7.52 (9H, m, Ar-H).

Analogous assignments could be done for the protons of the compounds **12b** and **12d** also from analysis of the ¹H NMR spectral data of their impure samples. It may be pointed out here that in each of these cases, the two geminal protons of -OCH₂-CH₃ were found to appear at two different positions as multiplets owing to their diastereotopic relationship.

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